

Generative Artificial Intelligence Tools: Usage Guidelines

Allowed or not allowed in learning activities and assessments?

LEVEL 0

LEVEL 1

LEVEL 2

LEVEL 3

LEVEL 4

The use of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) tools is restricted, if not banned altogether, because the teacher deems the use of these tools detrimental to the development of essential skills. These skills can be disciplinary as well as methodological, editorial, or informational. Given that the utilisation of GenAI necessitates the application of critical thinking, the learning activities and assessments are designed to facilitate the development of this skill without the use of GenAI.

In these situations, **the student produces the work.**

Heavy use of GenAI is allowed because the teacher expects students to be able to exercise critical thinking skills and judge the quality of the content produced by GenAI. It is further recommended that the proposed learning activities or assessments be utilized as a means of fostering critical thinking skills.

In these situations, the GenAI produces the preliminary work, while **the student ensures its quality by improving it.**

Prohibited Use

LEVEL 0 means that use is **prohibited**.

In this context, any reason that would suggest to a teacher that a GenAI has been used in an assignment is considered an infraction. and must be reported to the faculty disciplinary officer as specified in the [Academic Regulations](#).

Limited use

LEVEL 1 USE means that use is **permitted only to assist the student in relation to the subject of study or their use of language**.

In this context, the student is **required to declare how they used a GenAI** as specified by the teacher, otherwise the use will be considered an infraction.

For example:

Learning:

- Get inspired
- Generate ideas
- Explore a topic to better understand it
- Generate material to learn

Language:

- Identify your mistakes and have them explained to you
- Rephrase a text
- Generate an outline to help structure a text
- Translate a text

Targeted use

LEVEL 2 USE means that the use is **authorized to improve work produced by the student**.

In this context, the student is **required to declare how they used a GenAI** as specified by the teacher, otherwise the use will be considered an infraction.

For example:

- Analyze content
- Get feedback
- Evaluate the quality of your work based on criteria
- Ask to be confronted with your ideas, your approach
- Use problem-solving processes

Framed use

LEVEL 3 USE means that use is **authorized to produce work that will be improved**.

In this context, the student is **required to cite the content generated by the GenAI in accordance with the standards¹ or declare how they used a GenAI** as specified by the teacher, otherwise the use will be considered an infraction.

For example:

- Summarize or write parts of a text
- Create and adapt a text or an example of a product
- Perform mathematical calculations
- Write computer code
- Solve complex problems
- Answer a question
- Create images or other multimedia content

Free use

LEVEL 4 USE means that **no specific restrictions are imposed**.

In this context, the student is **required to cite the content generated by the GenAI in accordance with the standards¹ or declare how they used a GenAI** as specified by the teacher, otherwise the use will be considered an infraction.

This level includes all of the previous levels of authorization, from exploring to producing, as well as any other special tasks deemed complex.

A transparent approach to supervise GenAI tools in educational activities

A transparent approach requires the establishment of clear guidelines outlining the acceptable uses and conditions for the use of GenAI tools on a global or ad hoc basis. A teacher may determine that the use of these types of technologies is aligned with the learning objectives identified for their course. For example, the instructor may opt to integrate GenAI tools into the entirety of their course curriculum or into one or more distinct learning activities or assessments.

It is incumbent upon the teacher to clearly communicate the extent to which GenAI tools may be utilized by students in the context of each learning activity and assessment outlined in the course syllabus.

These levels of use are not prescribed by the institution. Rather, they serve as guidelines to frame the use of GenAI tools in learning activities and assessments. In addition to the course syllabus, the directives can be communicated on the course's Moodle website or in the assignment to ensure that students are informed at the beginning of the session. In short, it is now encouraged to specify the permitted uses in the teaching materials of each of the learning activities.

Levels of use have been determined to be inclusive of each other, but these may vary from one assignment to another depending on the competencies that are targeted. To avoid misunderstandings, the prescribed guidelines for learning activities and assessments should be clearly communicated to students in the course syllabus.

Beyond clearly communicating guidelines, make sure to:

- Design evaluation criteria that consider the appropriate use of GenAI in the proposed learning activities.
- Emphasize the importance of academic integrity by declaring the uses.
- Provide specific examples of acceptable and unacceptable uses of GenAI to help students better understand expectations.
- Encourage students to ask questions about using GenAI and provide clear and accessible answers.

¹ The presentation rules are explained in Cabana, M. et Beaudet, M. (2024). *Citation and Reference Guidelines: Use of GenAI in an Assignment* (E. Bowles & M. Beaudet, trad.). Université de Sherbrooke. [CC BY 4.0](#).

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Translated by Bowles, E. & Beaudet, M. (2024) from the original document by Cabana, M. et Côté, J.-A. (2024). [Balises d'utilisation des outils d'intelligence artificielle générative](#). Service de soutien à la formation, Université de Sherbrooke. Sous licence [CC BY 4.0](#).

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